

School Leaders' Leadership Skills, Ethical Values, and Adaptability as Predictors of School Climate: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach

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Abstract. A negative school climate poses a serious challenge in modern education, as it directly hinders teaching, learning, and overall school effectiveness. This study examined school climate by modeling the influence of school leaders' leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). A quantitative, non-experimental, was employed, involving 400 public school teachers in basic education schools in the Davao Region and randomly selected and the data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, multiple regression, and SEM. Results showed high ratings for leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability, and school climate, highlighting their role in promoting a positive school environment. Further, significant positive correlations between all independent variables and school climate, with adaptability (.670) and ethical values (.652) having the strongest associations, and leadership skills (.324) showing a moderate influence. Moreover, results showed that leadership skills ($\beta = .090$), ethical values ($\beta = .378$), and adaptability skills ($\beta = .434$) significantly predicted school climate, explaining 56.7% of its variance, with adaptability and ethical values as the strongest predictors. SEM also identified the best-fit model (Model 1), with adaptability and ethical values strongly influencing school climate, while leadership skills had minimal impact. The findings highlight the central role of transformational leadership qualities, including ethical values and adaptability, in shaping a positive and collaborative school climate, with implications for leadership practice, policy development, and future research.

Keywords: Adaptability skills; Ethical values; Leadership skills; School climate; Structural Equation Modeling Approach

Introduction

A negative school climate has become a major concern in today's educational environments, as recent studies continue to highlight ongoing issues within school settings (Yin, et. al., 2024). Teachers also report serious concerns about school climate, indicating that many school environments are perceived as less supportive, safe, or well-organized (Hammar Chiriac, et. al., 2023). Moreover, there is growing disagreement between students' and teachers' perceptions of school climate, which suggests a misalignment that undermines the school's relational and emotional environment (Hirata, et. al., 2024).

Research shows that a major global problem in school climate is the perceptual gap between teachers and school leaders. Data from the Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) 2018, covering 37 countries including the United States, Japan, Germany, and China, indicate that principals generally view the school climate more positively than teachers (Veletić, Price, & Olsen, 2023). This mismatch in perceptions can reduce teacher collaboration, lower job satisfaction, and strain relationships within schools, highlighting the need for aligned leadership and climate strategies. In Japan, recent large-sample research reports discrepancies between teachers' and students' perceptions, indicating that school climate remains a problematic situation in many schools (Hirata, et. al., 2024). Further, In the United States (New York City), researchers report persistent school-level climate problems linked to disciplinary practices and teacher perceptions, describing school climate as an ongoing problem for urban schools (Rodriguez, Welsh, and Daniels, 2024). Moreover, in China, national studies identify negative school climate as a notable problem observed across student populations (Yin, Su, and Li, 2024). Thus, the persistence of these concerns across different nations underscores that problematic school climate is a global issue that continues to challenge educational systems, regardless of context or geography.

In the Philippines, according to Mandapat and Farin (2021) secondary school teachers in Zambales reported that during the COVID-19 pandemic, dimensions of school climate — such as community engagement, peer relations, and physical environment — posed significant challenges. Furthermore, Gallego (2024) states that In Davao City, mathematics teachers have reported a negative school climate that leads to teacher burnout. Moreover, in Monkayo West District, Davao de Oro, public secondary teachers rated their school climate as problematic in terms of collegiality and professional collaboration (Gonzales and Diosco, 2024) hence, school climate has a problematic standing in creating a supportive and cohesive educational environment. Thus, school climate remains a pressing and persistent concern in the Philippine context, calling for focused attention and responsive interventions.

Consequently, a persistent negative school climate could intensify teacher burnout and turnover, and over the next decade or two gradually weaken student engagement and overall system performance, eventually straining the Department of Education's capacity to sustain quality education (Gallego, 2024 and Mok and Flynt, 2021). Several studies have examined the relationship between leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate across various contexts. However, there remains a lack of comprehensive empirical research in Region XI that applies structural equation modeling (SEM) to investigate these variables together. In fact, no existing study has integrated School Leaders' leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability skills in a single SEM analysis on school climate, as most literature focuses on only one or two of these factors. This gap underscores the significance of the present study in providing new insights and addressing the existing shortage of scientific evidence on school climate in Region XI.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the structural model of school climate by examining dimensions of school leaders' leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate. in basic education public and private schools in the Davao Region. Specifically, this study intended to:

1. What is the level of leadership skills of school leaders in terms of:
 - 1.1 Administrative Skills,
 - 1.2 Technical Skills,
 - 1.3 Personal Skills, and
 - 1.4 Social Skills
2. What is the level of ethical values of school leaders in terms of:
 - 2.1 Trustworthiness
 - 2.2 Respect,
 - 2.3 Responsibility,
 - 2.4 Fairness, and
 - 2.5 Caring
3. What is the level of adaptability skills of school leaders in terms of:
 - 3.1 Autonomy,
 - 3.2 Involvement,
 - 3.3 Innovation and Flexibility, and
 - 3.4 Clarity of Goals
4. What is the level of school climate in terms of:
 - 4.1 Learning and Innovation Workforce,
 - 4.2 Communication, and
 - 4.3 Life and Career,
5. To determine the significant relationship between leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate.
6. To determine the combined significant influence of the leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate.
7. To determine the best-fit model that explains the influence of leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study examined the structural relationships among school leaders' leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). It focused on the three key latent variables—leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability skills—as predictors of school climate. The study also considered the integrated influence of these variables within a single analytical model to determine their combined effects. The research was conducted in selected schools in Region XI, Philippines, and covered identified school leaders as respondents, with anonymized coding used to ensure confidentiality and ethical compliance.

Literature Review

Leadership Skills of School Leaders

Administrative and technical skills are essential leadership competencies that enable school leaders to effectively manage school operations and achieve educational goals. Administrative skills involve planning, organizing, coordinating, decision-making, resource allocation, and policy implementation to ensure the efficient functioning of the school organization, while technical skills pertain to instructional supervision, educational planning, curriculum management, and the utilization of educational technologies and systems necessary for effective school administration. Studies emphasize that school leaders with strong administrative and technical competencies contribute significantly to improved school performance, instructional quality, organizational effectiveness, and positive student outcomes by aligning school programs with strategic goals and adapting to emerging educational demands (Mduwile & Komariah, 2021; Caingcoy, 2020; Tan et al., 2021). These competencies also strengthen school leaders' capacity to address institutional challenges and support continuous educational improvement. Further, personal and social skills are essential leadership competencies that enable school leaders to effectively manage themselves and interact productively with others in the school community. Personal skills refer to individual characteristics and self-management abilities such as self-awareness, emotional regulation, adaptability, integrity, motivation, and decision-making, which are critical in enhancing leadership effectiveness. Social skills, on the other hand, involve the capacity to build positive interpersonal relationships, communicate effectively, collaborate with stakeholders, and foster a supportive and inclusive school climate. Studies highlight that school leaders with strong personal and social competencies demonstrate greater resilience, professionalism, and relational effectiveness, which contribute to improved teacher performance and organizational outcomes (Hourani et al., 2020; De Castro & Jimenez, 2022). These combined competencies play a vital role in strengthening leadership effectiveness and promoting a positive and productive school environment.

Ethical Values of School Leaders

Ethical values of school leaders refer to the moral principles that guide their behavior, decision-making, and leadership practices within the school environment. These values are essential in promoting integrity, accountability, and professionalism in school management, ensuring that leaders act in ways that uphold the welfare of learners and the school community. Trustworthiness, respect, responsibility, fairness, and caring are commonly identified dimensions of ethical leadership that shape how school leaders interact with stakeholders and implement policies. Studies emphasize that ethical leadership strengthens organizational trust, improves school climate, and enhances the credibility of school leaders in fulfilling their roles (Brown et al., 2020; Kalshoven et al., 2021). When school leaders demonstrate high ethical standards, they foster a culture of transparency and moral integrity within the institution. Furthermore, ethical leadership plays a significant role in influencing teacher behavior, student development, and overall school effectiveness. Trustworthiness builds confidence among stakeholders, while respect and fairness ensure equitable treatment and inclusive decision-making. Responsibility and caring, on the other hand, reflect the commitment of leaders to the welfare and development of both learners and teachers. Research indicates that school leaders who consistently demonstrate strong ethical values are more likely to create positive school environments characterized by trust, collaboration, and shared accountability (Kalshoven et al., 2021; Northouse, 2022). These ethical dimensions collectively contribute to sustainable school improvement and effective educational leadership.

Adaptability Skills of School Leaders

Adaptability skills of school leaders refer to their capacity to adjust effectively to changing educational environments, respond to emerging challenges, and implement appropriate strategies to sustain school improvement. These skills are critical in ensuring that school leaders remain responsive and resilient in dynamic educational contexts. Autonomy, involvement, innovation and flexibility, and clarity of goals are key dimensions of adaptability that reflect how leaders exercise independent decision-making, engage stakeholders, introduce new practices, and maintain direction in school operations. Research emphasizes that adaptive leadership enhances organizational resilience, supports continuous improvement, and strengthens leaders' ability to manage uncertainty in educational settings (Heifetz et al., 2020; Uhl-Bien & Arena, 2021). When school leaders demonstrate strong adaptability, they are better able to sustain effective school performance amid changing demands. Furthermore, adaptability is strongly associated with innovation-driven leadership and goal-oriented management in schools. Leaders who exhibit autonomy are more capable of making timely decisions, while involvement fosters collaboration and shared responsibility among stakeholders. Innovation and flexibility allow school leaders to implement creative solutions to institutional challenges, and clarity of goals ensures alignment of school efforts toward educational

objectives. Studies indicate that adaptive leadership practices contribute to improved organizational learning, increased stakeholder engagement, and enhanced institutional effectiveness in school systems (Uhl-Bien & Arena, 2021; Fullan, 2021). These dimensions collectively support a responsive and future-ready educational environment.

School Climate

School climate refers to the overall quality of the school environment as experienced by students, teachers, and stakeholders, including its norms, relationships, teaching practices, and organizational culture. A positive school climate is essential for promoting academic success, teacher satisfaction, and student well-being. The dimensions of learning and innovation workforce, communication, and life and career reflect the extent to which schools support professional growth, effective information exchange, and balanced personal and professional development. Research highlights that a supportive school climate fosters collaboration, enhances teaching effectiveness, and encourages continuous innovation in educational practices (Thapa et al., 2020; Wang & Degol, 2021). Schools with strong climates are more likely to achieve higher levels of performance and organizational stability. Moreover, school climate significantly influences both teaching and learning outcomes by shaping relationships and institutional culture. A learning and innovation workforce promotes professional development and creative instructional strategies, while effective communication ensures clarity, transparency, and coordination among stakeholders. Life and career balance supports teacher well-being, job satisfaction, and long-term retention. Studies indicate that positive school climate is strongly associated with improved student achievement, higher teacher motivation, and stronger organizational commitment within schools (Wang & Degol, 2021; Cohen et al., 2020). These factors collectively contribute to a healthy, productive, and sustainable educational environment.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed structural equation modeling (SEM) alongside a descriptive-correlational approach within a quantitative research framework to examine the influence of School Leaders' leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability skills on school climate (Babbie, 2016; Hair et al., 2018). The descriptive-correlational method investigated the relationships among these variables and their impact on school climate without experimental manipulation, identifying significant patterns and associations (Ormrod, 2016). SEM then was used to analyze the combined effects of these factors within a comprehensive model, accounting for possible mediating or moderating relationships (Hair et al., 2018). By integrating these methods, the study provided a structured understanding of how School Leaders' competencies shape the school climate, offering practical insights for administrators and educators to enhance organizational effectiveness (Hair et al., 2018; Ormrod, 2016).

Sampling Design

The study employed proportionate stratified random sampling to ensure balanced representation across subgroups. The population was grouped according to education levels: Elementary School (ES), Junior High School (JHS), and Senior High School (SHS). From a total population of 43,455, a sample of 400 respondents were selected, distributed as follows: 238 (ES), 132 (JHS), and 30 (SHS). This allocation reflects the proportion of each subgroup, ensuring accurate representation and maintaining statistical reliability (Ilyasu & Etikan, 2021).

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the Davao Region, located in the southern Philippines, which was composed of diverse urban and rural divisions such as Davao City, Digos City, Davao Oriental, and Davao del Norte, ensuring representation across varied educational contexts. The region was governed by the Department of Education (DepEd) Region XI, which oversaw both public and private basic education institutions in alignment with national standards and curriculum requirements. Based on the Basic Education Information System (BEIS) data for School Year 2025–2026, the region had 2,226 public schools serving approximately 1,199,102 learners across elementary, junior high school, and senior high school levels, supported by about 40,663 teaching personnel (Department of Education, 2026; Francisquete, 2025). This setting provided a comprehensive context for examining school leadership, ethical values, adaptability, and school climate across diverse educational environments in Region XI.

Research Participants

The respondents of the study were the public basic education teachers, principals, and school heads serving as school leaders in the Davao Region. They were selected based on the following criteria: (1) must be a public or private school employee serving as a teacher, principal, school head, or master teacher within Region XI; (2) must have at least one year of teaching experience; (3) may include relevant stakeholders; and (4) must be willing to participate in the study. Those with less than one year of teaching experience and those unwilling to participate were excluded.

Research Instrument

Data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire comprising four adapted instruments, each rated on a five-point Likert scale. First was the questionnaire on leadership skills, which was adapted from Ghanem and Abu Awwad (2019), comprising four dimensions: administrative skills, technical skills, personal skills, and social skills. The second part was adapted and modified from Josephson Institute of Ethics (2004) on ethical values questionnaire, categorized into trustworthiness, respect, responsibility, fairness, and caring. The third was the questionnaire on the adaptability skills of the school leaders, which was adapted from Atena (2018), comprising three dimensions: learning and innovation, communication, and life and career. Finally, to measure the dependent variable, school climate, the researcher was adapted the questionnaire from the study of Patterson et al. (2005). The questionnaire for this variable comprises four scales: autonomy, involvement, innovation and flexibility, and clarity of goals. All instruments underwent expert validation and pilot testing, yielding excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = .943 - .956$). Furthermore, ethical considerations were rigorously upheld throughout the study, including the acquisition of informed consent, assurance of participant anonymity, secure handling of data, and adherence to the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 and the guidelines set by the Philippine Health Research Ethics Board (PHREB).

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure followed a systematic and ethically grounded process to ensure the successful conduct of the study. Prior to data collection, the researcher secured the necessary approvals from the Dean of the Graduate School, the HCDC Research Ethics Committee (REC), the Regional Director of DepEd Region XI, and the respective Schools Division Superintendents. Upon approval, informed consent was obtained from all respondents after clearly explaining the study's objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits, thereby ensuring voluntary participation and adherence to ethical standards. The researcher then administered the questionnaires to the selected respondents, providing sufficient time for completion before retrieving and securing the instruments with strict confidentiality. Subsequently, the collected data were organized, tabulated, and prepared for statistical analysis, with the assistance of a statistician to ensure accurate data treatment and interpretation.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What is the level of leadership skills of school leaders in terms of administrative skills, technical skills, personal skills, and social skills?

Table 1. Level of leadership skills of school leaders in terms of administrative skills, technical skills, personal skills, and social skills

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Administrative Skills	3.76	Agree	Highly Proficient
Technical Skills	3.62	Agree	Highly Proficient
Personal Skills	3.75	Agree	Highly Proficient
Social Skills	3.36	Neutral	Moderately Proficient
Over-all Mean	3.62	Agree	Highly Proficient

Table 1 shows that leadership skills obtained an overall mean of 3.62 (SD = 0.755), interpreted as high, indicating that school leaders generally demonstrate strong competencies in managing their schools. Among the indicators, administrative skill had the highest mean of 3.76, followed by personal skill at 3.75, both high, suggesting effective administrative performance and strong personal leadership. Social skill recorded the lowest mean of 3.36, interpreted as moderate, indicating a need for further development in interpersonal and relational abilities. This result supports the findings of recent studies emphasizing the

critical role of school leaders' leadership skills in fostering productive environments and improving institutional outcomes. De Castro and Jimenez (2022) found that principals' leadership significantly influenced teachers' performance, while Wang and Dapat (2023) reported strong effects on school climate, including faculty collaboration and stability. These studies suggest that consistent leadership competencies enhance positive perceptions among staff. However, Simbre et al. (2023) and Dursun, Yıldız, and Yüksel (2022) indicate that the impact of leadership skills may vary depending on contextual factors such as culture, collaboration, and administrative support.

Research Question 2: What is the level of ethical values of school leaders in terms of trustworthiness, respect, responsibility, fairness and caring?

Table 2. Level of ethical values of school leaders in terms of trustworthiness, respect, responsibility, fairness, and caring

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Trustworthiness	3.49	Agree	Highly Good
Respect	3.79	Agree	Highly Good
Responsibility	3.97	Agree	Highly Good
Fairness	3.86	Agree	Highly Good
Caring	3.65	Agree	Highly Good
Over-all Mean	3.75	Agree	Highly Good

Table 2 shows the ethical values of school leaders, which obtained an overall mean of 3.75 (SD = 0.657), also high, showing that school leaders consistently exhibit ethical principles. Responsibility had the highest mean of 3.97, followed by fairness (3.86) and respect (3.79), while trustworthiness scored the lowest at 3.49, yet still high, reflecting generally positive ethical conduct. This result supports the findings of studies highlighting the importance of ethical leadership in fostering trust, fairness, and collaboration in schools. Montales (2024) and Warsi et al. (2025) found that ethical and transformational leadership positively influence motivation, accountability, and supportive school environments. However, Kaleem, Din, and Rehman (2023) and Alnisyar and Nur (2024) note that ethical leadership may vary across schools depending on context, leadership style, and management practices.

Research Question 3: What is the level of adaptability skills in terms of learning and innovation workforce, communication, and life and career?

Table 3. Level of adaptability skills in terms of learning and innovation workforce, communication, and life and career

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Learning and Innovation	4.16	Agree	Highly Manifested
Communication	4.13	Agree	Highly Manifested
Life and Career	3.90	Agree	Highly Manifested
Over-all Mean	4.06	Agree	Highly Manifested

Table 3 shows the adaptability skills which obtained an overall mean of 4.06 (SD = 0.545), interpreted as high, indicating that school leaders effectively adjust to changes and challenges. Learning and innovation had the highest mean of 4.16, followed by communication (4.13), while life and career scored 3.90, still high, highlighting strong professional adaptability. This result supports studies highlighting the importance of adaptability in school leadership, enabling leaders to respond effectively to changing policies, challenges, and technological demands. Warsi et al. (2025) and Riaz, Shahzad, and Kubra (2024) found that adaptable and flexible leadership fosters dynamic learning environments, teacher empowerment, and school effectiveness. However, Patampang et al. (2024) and Sayman and Atienzar (2023) note that adaptability may vary depending on contextual factors, institutional support, and external challenges, indicating that its manifestation is not always consistent across schools.

Research Question 4: What is the level of school climate in terms of autonomy, involvement, innovation and flexibility, and clarity of goals?

Table 4. Level of school climate in terms of autonomy, involvement, innovation and flexibility, and clarity of goals

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Autonomy	4.02	Agree	Highly Manifested
Involvement	3.82	Agree	Highly Manifested
Innovation and Flexibility	4.02	Agree	Highly Manifested
Clarity of Goals	4.00	Agree	Highly Manifested
Over-all Mean	3.96	Agree	Highly Manifested

Table 4 shows the school climate which obtained an overall mean of 3.96 (SD = 0.657), high, suggesting a generally positive and supportive environment, highly manifested. Autonomy, innovation, and flexibility scored the highest at 4.02, followed by clarity of goals (4.00), while involvement was lowest at 3.82, yet still high, indicating active stakeholder participation. This result supports studies emphasizing the role of effective leadership and collaboration in fostering positive school climates. Villan (2024) and Sayman and Atienzar (2023) found that supportive leadership and teacher collaboration contribute to high perceptions of school climate and enhance teaching effectiveness. However, Dursun et al. (2022) and Kaleem et al. (2023) note that school climate may vary across institutions, as leadership challenges, organizational support, and institutional culture can influence perceptions.

Research Question 5: To determine the significant relationship between leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate.

Table 5. Correlation Table

	School Climate		Decision on Ho at 0.05 level of significance	Interpretation
	r	p-value		
Leadership Skills	.324	.000	Reject	Significant
Ethical Values	.652	.000	Reject	Significant
Adaptability Skills	.670	.000	Reject	Significant

Presented in Table 5 is the correlation analysis showing the relationship between leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate. The results reveal that all independent variables have significant positive relationships with school climate. The table indicates that adaptability skills have the strongest relationship with school climate, with an r-value of .670 and a p-value of .000. This result suggests a strong positive correlation, indicating that as the adaptability skills of school leaders increase, the school climate tends to improve. This implies that leaders who demonstrate strong administrative, technical, personal, and social skills, by adapting to changes, fostering innovation, and communicating effectively, play a key role in cultivating a positive school climate. The evidence supports the findings of Riaz, Shahzad, and Kubra (2024) and Sayman and Atienzar (2023), who reported that adaptable leadership, marked by flexibility and responsiveness, positively influences collaboration, teacher motivation, and school climate. However, Villan (2024) and De Castro and Jimenez (2022) found that the impact of adaptability may be weaker, as other leadership dimensions, such as instructional leadership and organizational management, also affect school climate. Following this is ethical values, which also demonstrate a strong positive relationship with school climate, as reflected by an r-value of .652 and a p-value of .000. This indicates that higher levels of ethical values among school leaders, such as fairness, responsibility, and respect, are associated with a more positive and supportive school climate. This result supports the findings of Alnisyar and Nur (2024) and Warsi et al. (2025), who reported that ethical leadership, emphasizing integrity, fairness, and moral responsibility, positively influences teacher performance, motivation, and school climate. However, Simbre et al. (2023) and Patampang et al. (2024) suggest that the impact of ethical leadership may be moderate, as other factors such as leadership styles, communication practices, and institutional support also affect school climate. On the other hand, leadership skills show the lowest relationship with school climate among the variables, with an r-value of .324 and a p-value of .000. Although the correlation is comparatively lower, it is still statistically significant, suggesting that leadership skills also contribute to the improvement of school climate. This present finding supports the study of Dursun, Yıldız, and Yüksel (2022)

and Kaleem, Din, and Rehman (2023), who reported that leadership positively influences school climate but is moderated by factors such as teacher collaboration and institutional culture. In contrast, Montales (2024) and Wang and Dapat (2023) found stronger effects, indicating that the impact of leadership skills on school climate may vary across educational contexts. Since the p-values of all variables (.000) are less than the 0.05 level of significance, the relationships are considered statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypotheses stating that there is no significant relationship between leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate are rejected.

Research Question 6: To determine the combined significant influence of the leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate.

Table 6. Regression Table

Model	School Climate			t	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Beta			
		Standard Error			
(Constant)	.128	.176		.725	.469
Leadership Skills	.080	.031	.090	2.554	.011
Ethical Values	.392	.043	.378	9.201	.000
Adaptability Skills	.511	.047	.434	10.816	.000

As shown in Table 6, leadership skills had a standardized beta coefficient of .090, indicating a 9.0% influence on school climate. With a p-value of .011, which is below the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming a significant relationship between leadership skills and school climate. This implies that a one-unit increase in leadership skills corresponds to a .090-unit increase in school climate. This result supports the findings of Özhan (2025) and Alinsunurin (2020), who reported that various leadership models positively influence school climate by shaping relationships, organizational culture, and learning environments. However, Carbonero (2026) and Jensena, Solheimb, and Olsenc (2024) suggest that the effect of leadership on school climate may be indirect or mediated by other factors, indicating that leadership alone may not always serve as a primary predictor of broader climate outcomes. Ethical values demonstrated a standardized beta coefficient of .378, reflecting a 37.8% influence on school climate. The p-value of .000, below 0.05, led to rejection of the null hypothesis, validating a significant relationship. This indicates that a one-unit increase in ethical values results in a .378-unit increase in school climate. This finding supports the study of Özdoğru and Sarier (2024), who reported that ethical leadership strongly enhances organizational trust, justice, and teacher motivation, contributing positively to school climate. However, Neves et al. (2025) and related systematic reviews indicate that the impact of ethical leadership on school climate may vary depending on contextual factors, organizational support, and cultural perceptions, suggesting that its effects can be mediated rather than directly predictive. Adaptability skills obtained a standardized beta coefficient of .434, showing a 43.4% influence on school climate. With a p-value of .000, also below 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming a significant relationship. This suggests that a one-unit increase in adaptability skills corresponds to a .434-unit increase in school climate. This outcome supports the findings of McLean, Taylor, and Sandilos (2023), who reported that teacher adaptability positively influences self-efficacy and relational aspects of the classroom, with stronger effects in more positive school climates. However, Patac and Doronio (2025) and related research suggest that adaptability's impact may be context-specific or outcome-bound, acting as a mediator or moderator rather than directly predicting broader school climate, indicating its influence is not universally consistent. The overall regression model demonstrated an R-value of .753, indicating a strong correlation between the predictors (leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability skills) and school climate. The R² value of .567 shows that 56.7% of the variance in school climate is explained by these predictors, with the remaining 43.3% attributed to other factors. The model was statistically significant, as indicated by an F-ratio of 172.808 and a p-value of .000, which is below the 0.05 significance threshold. Finally, Table 3 presented the derived regression formula as: $SC = .080(LS) + .392(EV) + .511(AS) + .128$, where SC represents School Climate, LS refers to Leadership Skills, EV denotes Ethical Values, and AS stands for Adaptability Skills. This regression equation indicates that school climate can be predicted based on the combined influence of leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability skills, with .128 serving as the constant value when all predictor variables are held at zero. These current findings support the study of Özdoğru, Sarier, and Korucuoglu (2025), who reported that combining leadership and school climate moderately predicts educational outcomes, highlighting the value of integrating multiple factors in models of school environment. Similarly, research indicates that combining

personal competencies and organizational variables provides stronger explanatory power for school climate than single predictors. However, empirical studies show that even combined models leave substantial unexplained variance due to systemic, policy, and contextual factors, suggesting that leadership, ethical, and adaptability skills alone partially explain school climate outcomes.

Research Question 7: To determine the best-fit model that explains the influence of leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate.

Table 7. Test of Best – Fit Model on School Climate among Public Schools

Index	Standard Criteria	Model 1 (Best Fit)	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
CMIN/df	< 5	1.538	2.802	2.217	1.760	1.684
P-value	> .05	0.053	0.000	0.000	0.019	0.019
NFI	>.95	0.971	0.944	0.965	0.984	0.972
TLI	>.95	0.975	0.916	0.950	0.976	0.973
CFI	>.95	0.990	0.962	0.980	0.992	0.988
GFI	>.95	0.976	0.954	0.975	0.985	0.982
RMSEA	< .05	0.037	0.067	0.055	0.044	0.041
P close	>.05	0.916	0.013	0.292	0.643	0.720

Illustrated in Table 7 are the derived values of the goodness-of-fit indices used to determine the best-fit model. These include Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom (CMIN/df), Probability Value (P-value), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Tucker Lewis Index (TLI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and Probability Close (P-close), along with their corresponding standard criteria. Shown in the table is the comparison of five hypothesized models to identify which model best explains the relationships among leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate. Models 2 to 5 failed to meet several of the required criteria for a good model fit. Model 2, despite having an acceptable CMIN/df value of 2.802, has a p-value of .000 which is below the required > .05 level, indicating poor fit. Its RMSEA value of .067 also exceeds the acceptable threshold, and some indices like NFI (.944) and TLI (.916) fall below .95. Similarly, Model 3 shows improvement with acceptable indices such as NFI (.965), TLI (.950), CFI (.980), and GFI (.975), but its p-value (.000) and RMSEA (.055) still do not fully satisfy the criteria. Model 4 and Model 5 both show acceptable CMIN/df values (1.760 and 1.684, respectively) and good fit indices; however, their p-values (.019 for both) remain below the acceptable level, indicating that the models still have significant discrepancies. In contrast, Model 1 demonstrates the best overall fit among all models. Its CMIN/df value of 1.538 is well within the acceptable limit of less than 5. The p-value of .053 exceeds the required > .05 threshold, indicating no significant difference between the observed data and the model. Furthermore, all goodness-of-fit indices—NFI (.971), TLI (.975), CFI (.990), and GFI (.976)—are above the required .95 level, reflecting a strong model fit. The RMSEA value of .037 is below .05, indicating a close fit, while the P-close value of .916 further confirms that the model fits the data very well.

Figure 1. Best Fit Model on School Climate

Legend:

Leadership_Skill	= Leadership Skill	COM	= Communication
Ethical_Values	= Ethical Values	LAC	= Life and Career
Adaptability_Skills	= Adaptability Skills	AUT	= Autonomy
School_Climate	= School Climate	INVOL	= Involvement
AS	= Administrative Skill	IA	= Innovation and Flexibility
TS	= Technical Skill	COG	= Clarity of Goals
PS	= Personal Skill	RPBLTY	= Responsibility
SS	= Social Skill	FN	= Fairness
TW	= Trustworthiness	CR	= Caring
RP	= Respect	LAIW	= Learning and Innovation workforce

Figure 1 presents the best-fit structural equation model on school climate among public schools. The model illustrates the relationships between the latent variables—leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability skills—and the endogenous variable, school climate. The results reveal that adaptability skills have the strongest direct effect on school climate ($\beta = 1.05$), followed by ethical values ($\beta = 0.97$), while leadership skills show a minimal and slightly negative direct effect ($\beta = -0.07$). This implies that a one-unit increase in adaptability skills leads to a 1.05 unit increase in school climate, while ethical values contribute 0.97, and leadership skills have negligible influence. These findings indicate that adaptability skills and ethical values play a major role in improving school climate, while leadership skills have a relatively small direct influence. This suggests that school leaders who are highly adaptable and demonstrate strong ethical behavior are more effective in fostering a positive school environment compared to relying on leadership skills alone. The model also shows that leadership skills are measured through AS, TS, PS, and SS; ethical values through TW, RP, RPBLTY, FN, and CR; adaptability skills through LAIW, COM, and LAC; and school

climate through AUT, INVOL, IAF, and COG. These indicators strongly represent their respective constructs, while the error terms account for unexplained variance.

Furthermore, the model indicates that leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability skills are interrelated, as shown by their covariances (e.g., leadership skills and ethical values = 0.12, ethical values and adaptability skills = 0.04). This means that improving one competency may also positively influence the others. Overall, the findings highlight that adaptability, and ethical values are crucial in shaping a positive school climate. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no structural model that best fits the relationships among leadership skills, ethical values, adaptability skills, and school climate is rejected, indicating that the proposed model is supported by the data. The analysis indicates that Model 1 is the most reliable framework for understanding the interrelationships among school leaders' leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability skills, and their causal effects on school climate. The results from the best-fit model highlight that transformational behaviors among school leaders can foster a positive and collaborative school environment, where teachers and staff are motivated to engage, support one another, and collectively contribute to an improved school climate (Alzoraiki et al., 2024; Caharian & Cabanlit, 2024). Moreover, the finding aligns with Transformational Leadership Theory, which emphasizes leaders' ability to inspire, empower, and ethically guide followers toward shared goals (Burns, 1978; Bass & Riggio, 2020). Schools that cultivate leaders with strong ethical values, adaptable practices, and effective leadership skills are more likely to experience cohesive climates that promote collaboration, trust, and organizational effectiveness (Özdoğru & Sarier, 2024). The practical implication of the model informs strategies to enhance school climate and organizational well-being. By developing school leaders who demonstrate adaptability, ethical behavior, and transformational leadership skills, educational institutions can strengthen teacher commitment, foster positive interpersonal interactions, and build supportive learning environments (Wang et al., 2024; Laursen, 2025). This alignment not only enhances teacher motivation and resilience but also contributes to a more stable and productive school climate (McLean et al., 2023). Policymakers and school administrators are encouraged to adopt this model as a guiding framework for leadership development programs, professional training initiatives, and strategic interventions aimed at improving climate outcomes. Henceforth, future research should continue exploring complementary variables that could further refine the model. Incorporating additional constructs such as teacher engagement, organizational support, or student outcomes may reveal nuanced pathways through which leadership, ethics, and adaptability shape school climate (Özdoğru et al., 2025). Despite this, the consistent explanatory power of Model 1 in linking leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability to school climate solidifies its value as a primary framework for advancing leadership practice in education. Its integration into policy, professional development, and school management will help ensure sustained improvements in school climate and institutional effectiveness (Ozdogru, Sarier, & Korucuoglu, 2025).

Ethical Considerations

The potential harm in this study includes risks to respondents' privacy, confidentiality, and emotional well-being. These risks were mitigated by adhering to the ethical standards set by DOST-PHREB and CHED, ensuring informed consent, and respecting participants' rights. The study received ethical clearance from the HCDC Society for Moral Integrity and Legal Ethics (SMILE) Ethics Review Committee with Ethics Reference Number 59827489, Series SMILE-2025-550. Strict privacy measures were implemented, with identifying information coded and securely stored, and data properly disposed of after use. Respondents were free to withdraw from the study without repercussions and could skip questions that caused discomfort. Fair selection procedures, transparency, and researcher competence further strengthened the integrity of the study. These measures helped minimize potential harm and uphold ethical research practices, particularly in education-related social policy research.

Conclusion

The study identified a best-fit model explaining the influence of school leaders' leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability skills on school climate. The results show that these three variables are significantly associated with and collectively contribute to the formation of a positive school climate. Among the variables examined, leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability skills work in an integrated manner, suggesting that effective school leadership is multidimensional in nature. The findings further support the Transformational Leadership Theory, which emphasizes the role of leaders in guiding, influencing, and aligning organizational conditions toward positive outcomes. In addition, the model underscores that school climate is strengthened when leaders consistently demonstrate sound decision-making, ethical conduct, and flexibility in responding to changing educational demands. These elements

collectively help explain variations in school climate within the study context. Overall, the study contributes empirical evidence on the relationship between leadership-related factors and school climate, reinforcing the importance of transformational leadership practices in educational settings.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it is recommended that school administrators and educational policymakers strengthen programs that develop school leaders' leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability, as these factors significantly influence school climate. Specifically, leadership development initiatives should include structured training modules on transformational leadership practices, with emphasis on ethical decision-making, effective communication, and adaptive management in school settings. These programs should be implemented on a regular basis and reinforced through mentoring or coaching systems to ensure practical application in day-to-day school operations. School administrators are encouraged to establish mentoring arrangements where experienced leaders guide newly appointed or less experienced school heads in applying ethical and adaptive leadership practices. Schools should also implement structured feedback systems, such as periodic teacher surveys and consultation meetings, to continuously assess leadership effectiveness and school climate conditions. To further enhance school climate, schools may institutionalize collaborative practices such as professional learning communities (PLCs), team-based instructional planning, and peer support mechanisms among teachers. Recognition systems should also be clearly defined and consistently applied to acknowledge exemplary performance and strengthen motivation among staff. In addition, school policies should explicitly integrate ethical standards and adaptive problem-solving procedures to guide leaders and staff in addressing academic and administrative concerns in a consistent and transparent manner. For future research, it is recommended that longitudinal studies be conducted to examine the long-term effects of leadership skills, ethical values, and adaptability on school climate. Researchers may also include additional variables such as teacher engagement, organizational support, and student outcomes to further explain the remaining 43.3% variance in school climate and provide deeper insights into effective school management practices.

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